

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE STATUS OF A PEDAGOGUE IN MODERN EDUCATION

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Abstract: In the article, the socio-philosophical aspects of securing the status of a pedagogue, its necessity, current issue, and its socio-philosophical classification and characteristics, as well as its importance in modern education, were analyzed in this process.

Key words: pedagogue, status of pedagogue, integration, globalization, social, philosophical, transformation.

INTRODUCTION

The problem of personal principle in modern education is very indicative and in a sense paradoxical. On the one hand, philosophical and humanistic thinking in general focused on the human personality from the 19th century, and it became one of the central topics of research in various directions and schools. In general, even in directions considered sociocentric, the individual had the most important role as a driving force in the socio-historical process. In addition, in psychology there has been a shift of research from the psychophysiological field to the inner world of a person, in sociology directions are being developed that give priority to the personal element in social processes.

But, on the other hand, in contrast to this leading trend in social and humanitarian knowledge, the trend of depersonalization, that is, the removal of the personality of the teacher from the educational process, is becoming more and more evident in modern education. This tendency reflected, first of all, the systemic crisis of modern technocratic civilization, the characteristics of which were clearly manifested in the field of human education (education, formation, training). At the same time, the growing motivation of depersonalization in theoretical work has a significant impact on educational practice and, therefore, on social processes in general.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

The problem of the role of the teacher's personality in education is multifaceted, it is related to many different studies in the field of social philosophy, psychology, anthropology, general theory of personality, as well as personal aspects of education.

In the 20th century, L. Kohlberg, K. Mannheim, E. Munier, P. Sorokin, A. Toynbee, J. Habermas, M. Heidegger and others made a great contribution to socio-philosophical research on the problem of the individual and society.

A. V. Brushlinsky, L. S. Vygotsky, E. V. Ilyenkov, S. L. Rubinshtein (20th century) and others made a special contribution to the development of socio-philosophical aspects of the problem of the teacher's role in education. However, despite many studies, the problem of the role of the teacher in modern education has not been studied enough.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Modern education is characterized by the trend of depersonalization (withdrawal of the teacher from the educational process), which manifests itself in technological and postmodern pedagogical trends. These trends are pedagogical projections of the corresponding philosophical and worldview trends in world culture. Classical humanist philosophical and pedagogical traditions oppose these trends.

Socio-pedagogical ideal is always, overtly or covertly, the target direction of the educational process. It includes the following components: a) the ideal of the person who leads the teacher himself and guides the student in the process of teaching and educating, b) the ideal of pedagogical activity (styles and methods of teaching and educating) . The socio-pedagogical ideal has the following aspects: purposeful (the main goal of education); value (the highest value in education), moral (the qualities and characteristics that should be cultivated in a student and, accordingly, the qualities and characteristics that should be the perfect image of a coach-teacher) and methodical (education and educational programs, methodological systems).

Aspects of the socio-pedagogical ideal in humanitarian traditions have the following content: a) the goal of education is to develop a child as a socially mature, creatively active and moral person, a holistic worldview based on deep meaningful knowledge of the worldview. world and man (goal); b) confirmation of a person as a carrier of high values (value); c) recognition of the leading role in the educational process for the teacher-mentor, who is the bearer of the main features of the pedagogical ideal, responsible for repeating the cultural, cognitive and moral experience (moral) of society; d) use of appropriate methods and methods in teaching and upbringing (methodology).

The need for the teacher's personality in the process of teaching and in the formation of the student's personality is related to the hierarchy of knowledge and the process of cognition itself. At the level of vital consciousness, any technological information devices are accepted, where the role of the teacher's personality is reduced to that of the programmer. The personal factor becomes more important at the level of formation of a comprehensive, meaningful

knowledge system. At the level of high-value components of knowledge, that is, the need for personal, creative participation of the teacher in forming the student's life directions increases even more.

Education is one of the most important social institutions and plays an important role in the process of forming a holistic system of values and knowledge of a person, thereby ensuring the stimulation and implementation of optimization processes in society. This position has been supported by humanist philosophical and pedagogical traditions for many centuries, on the basis of which a humanist socio-pedagogical ideal was formed. This ideal is embodied in various changes and forms, but it has always helped to be inherited from generation to generation, embodied in certain laws of human existence, high spiritual destiny of man, masterpieces of world culture.

The study of growing humanization processes in a non-classical society has an already established tradition - the specific features of this type of worldview are clearly defined in the works of many domestic and foreign authors. "Technological" pedagogy is inextricably linked with pragmatic market relations, within which the individual is not considered as a person, but only as a performer. This approach is gaining ground in the field of education and upbringing of a person, as a result of which there is a complete orientation to programmed education and early narrow specialization. At the same time, the use of various audio-visual tools and virtual worlds created with the help of modern computer technologies is absolute, harming the live communication between the teacher and the student.

Postmodernism rejects the classic ideals of the Enlightenment era and the classic humanist image of man; it is characterized by the criticism of classical humanism and the rejection of any universality - laws, rules, norms and values. Attempts by supporters of postmodernism to present their teachings as an objective example of human development can hardly be called successful. Many foreign and domestic authors reveal the borderline nature of their main ideas, convincingly justifying the complete inconsistency of their claims to legitimacy. The rapid development of this direction in pedagogy began in the West in the second half of the 20th century and was reflected in changes in the conceptual apparatus of pedagogy, the value of teachers, and a change in the philosophical and methodological direction. This, in turn, led to a number of negative consequences in the theory and practice of modern education.

Based on the comparative historical analysis of the development of ideas about the role of the teacher in the humanist tradition in Western European and

Russian cultures, we were able to explain the humanist socio-pedagogical ideal. Aspects of this ideal in the most general form describe the pedagogical activity itself (regardless of historical, social and other conditions) and have a corresponding humanistic content: the person is the highest value (aspect of value); the goal of education is to develop a child's personality as a creative person rooted in society, who has a holistic worldview based on deep meaningful knowledge of the world and man (objective aspect); raising a child using only methods and methods that optimally correspond to the bio-social, spiritual nature of the entire pedagogical process and, at the same time, correspond to the individual characteristics of a particular child (methodical aspect); The highest ideal, the bearer of moral example, is the personality of the teacher (moral aspect).

CONCLUSION

Recently, many researchers have focused their attention on the philosophical and methodological foundations of modern pedagogical systems. The most pressing issues are widely discussed in educational institutions, in the press, and at scientific conferences; attempts are being made to develop new approaches and concepts; Various studies are being conducted. All this confirms the need for a deep understanding of the complex processes in modern education..

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